

eDNA Aqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

PLAN OVERVIEW

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline.be

Title: eDNAqua-Plan

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Template: Template to document the data management of aquatic eDNA projects

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The DMP can be created directly in the DMPonline.be platform for all Belgian research institutes by selecting “Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO)” as the primary research organization and “Template to document the data management of aquatic eDNA projects” in the DMP template list:

DMP ONLINE | BE My Dashboard Create plans Reference Help Sofie Derycke

Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) <https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en/>
Data Manager

Create a new plan

Before you get started, we need some information about your research project to set you up with the best DMP template for your needs.

* What research project are you planning?

mock project for testing, practice, or educational purposes

* Select the primary research organisation
Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) - or - No research organisation associated with this plan or my research organisation is not listed

* Select the primary funding organisation
--Select funder-- - or - No funder associated with this plan or my funder is not listed

Which DMP template would you like to use?
 We found multiple DMP templates corresponding to your funder.

For research organizations outside Belgium, the template is provided below. By answering the questions and saving the word file, the DMP can be uploaded to the management system of the research institute.

Project metadata							
Sample metadata							
Additional environmental data							
Samples for eDNA							
Samples for bulkDNA							
Samples for morphological analyses							
Samples for environmental measurements							
Experimental conditions							
Sampling protocols							
Methodological protocols							
Extracted DNA							
PCR standard data							
eLow Quant Data							
Targeted assay amplification data							
Libraries for sequencing							
Experiment/run metadata							
Raw DNA sequence data							
Metagenome assemblies							
Bioinformatic code							
Data processing code							
Raw ASV/OTU table							
Processed ASV/OTU table							
Reference library							
Custom reference library code							
Non-curated sequence/taxa table							
Curated sequence/taxa table							

Species occurrence data from morphological analyses							
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If you reuse existing datasets (measurements, sequencing data, ...) or datatypes (lab protocols, scripts,...), please specify the source by using a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, Handle, URL etc.) per dataset or data type. If the source data is not published, then clearly describe the origin of the data (e.g. previous project, ongoing study, etc...), the current status (e.g. unpublished, under embargo, still being processed, ...), who owns the data (e.g. your institution, collaborators, ...) and the conditions for reuse in the current project (e.g. internal reuse only, access limited to named researchers, usage following a data sharing agreement, ...)

Answer:

Are there any ethical issues concerning the creation and/or use of the data (e.g. experiments on humans or animals, dual use)? Describe these issues in the comment section. Please refer to specific datasets or data types when appropriate.

- Human data
- animal data
- dual use (=use for defense or other military use)
- none
- other

Answer:

Will you process personal data? If so, briefly describe the kind of personal data you will use in the "Additional information" section, and specify whether you have obtained consent (e.g. GDPR in the EU) and whether you will be anonymising any personal information.

- Yes
- No

Answer:

Does your work have potential for commercial valorization (e.g. tech transfer, for example spin-offs, commercial exploitation, ...)? If so, please comment per dataset or data type where appropriate in the "Additional information" section.

- Yes
- No

Answer:

Do existing 3rd party agreements restrict exploitation or dissemination of the data you (re)use (e.g. Material/Data transfer agreements/ research collaboration agreements)? If so, please explain in the comment section to what data they relate and what restrictions are in place.

- Yes
- No

Answer:

Are there any other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, to be managed related to the data you (re)use? If so, please explain in the comment section to what data they relate and which restrictions will be asserted.

- Yes
- No

Answer:

Is there any indigenous knowledge involved related to the data you generate or (re)use? If so, please explain in the “Additional Information” section to which datasets this knowledge relates and how the CARE principles will be applied (see e.g. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-023-02161-2>)

- Yes
- No

Answer:

DATAMANAGEMENT WORKFLOW

In this section, more information is given on how the datasets listed in the table in the “Research Data summary” section are created and managed. The workflow of eDNA projects typically includes: 1/ collection of biological and/or environmental samples, 2/ process samples in the lab (e.g., extracted DNA,PCRs), 3/ obtain raw data (e.g., raw sequence files), 4/ process the raw data (e.g. ASV tables, taxonomy tables, ...), 5/ analyse the processed data (statistics, plots,...), 6/ publish datasets. A description of how the datasets for these components are being obtained, stored and tracked is needed for adequate management of the eDNA data.

Describe how physical samples (e.g. field samples) are collected and stored. A general description is sufficient. Provide at least the sampling area, the sampling medium (sediment, water, ...), the sampling device (eg Niskin rosette, passive samplers, autonomous eDNA sampler, etc), the type of samples (eg water bottles, filters, gauze, specimens), etc.

Answer:

Describe what sample metadata are collected, how it is recorded, where it is stored, and what data standards are used.

Think of geographical coordinates, sampling date, abiotic parameters (salinity, water temperature, chemicals, pollutants, turbidity, ...), sampling depth ...

Answer:

Describe in brief how the samples are processed for eDNA analyses (e.g. metabarcoding, qPCR, metagenomics, primer assays used, etc...). Where will the processed samples be stored, and how are they associated with the Sample IDs and the metadata. Where will the detailed lab protocols and metadata of the processed samples (e.g. DNA concentration, filtered volume, etc) be stored?

Answer:

Describe how the raw eDNA data are obtained (e.g. demultiplexed Illumina sequencing reads, amplification data, targeted assays,...)? Where will they be stored? How will it be backed up?

Answer:

Describe the main steps on how the raw eDNA data will be processed and list the processed datasets that will be generated. How will these processed data be associated with the raw data and sample data? Where will they be stored? Provide information on where scripts and code for processing of the raw data will be stored.

Answer:

Describe how the processed eDNA data will be analysed. Think of statistical analyses, diversity analyses, plots, calculations that will be used to analyse the data. What format is your analysis metadata (eg, scripts, details on analysis workflow)? Where will it be stored and how will it be backed up? How will these data be associated with raw data and sample data?

Answer:

What quality control procedures will be applied in the lab to the raw data, analyzed results, and the sample metadata. Examples of quality control procedures:

- gross error checks for data that fall outside of physically realistic ranges (e.g. impossible data or GPS)
- use of the FAIRRefier tool to check for metadata vocabulary and completeness
- peer review (e.g., two people will independently inspect sample metadata for errors)
- comparisons made with other independent sources of the same measurement;
- blanks or controls used during field collection and molecular processing to identify contamination
- filtering of samples or sequencing data (eg removal of singleton ASVs,...)

Answer:

Which data will be retained for at least five years (or longer, in agreement with other retention policies that are applicable) after the end of the project? In case some data cannot be preserved, clearly state the reasons for this (e.g. legal or contractual restrictions, storage/budget issues, institutional policies...).

Answer:

Where will these data be archived (stored and curated for the long-term)?

Answer:

What are the expected costs for data preservation during the expected retention period? How will these costs be covered?

Answer:

DATA SUBMISSION/PUBLICATION

As a final step, all datasets, protocols, bioinformatic workflows and analytical code produced throughout the workflow should be deposited in open repositories, several of which provide data validation, standardisation and persistent identifiers to enable long-term accessibility and interoperability.

Recommended FAIR Data Sharing Practices:

1. Sample metadata and raw sequence data: submit to INSDC repositories (ENA, NCBI, DDBJ) to ensure linkage of sequence data with BioProject/BioSample metadata.
2. Protocols and code: publish laboratory protocols, bioinformatic workflows and analytical code on open platforms such as Github, protocols.io and WorkflowHub. The BeBOP (Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices, a UN Ocean Decade project, Samuel et al. 2021) provides several templates for eDNA laboratory protocols.
3. Derived biodiversity data: publish inferred taxon occurrences, sequences and metadata to GBIF or OBIS (for marine data) using the Darwin Core Standard with the DNA-derived data extension. This can be easily done using the Metabarcoding Toolkit (MDT) and the FAIRe2MDT R script.
4. Additional data components outputs: archive remaining data components (e.g., targeted assay data, raw ASV/OTU tables) in open repositories such as Dryad, Zenodo or Figshare, or as journal supplements. These repositories provide long term storage but do not allow indexing.
5. Persistent identifiers: ensure all datasets, protocols and code are published in repositories with a permanent online address (URL or DOI), and reference them in data-accessibility statements and relevant metadata fields (e.g., FAIRe checklist: seq_archive, code_repo, associated_resource).

Will the data (or part of the data) be made available for reuse after/during the project? Explain per dataset or data type which data will be made available. If access is restricted, please specify who will be able to access the data and under what conditions.

Answer:

Are there any factors that restrict or prevent the sharing of (some of) the data (e.g. as defined in an agreement with a 3rd party, legal restrictions)? Please explain per dataset or data type where appropriate.

Answer:

When will the data be made available? We recommend making the data available as fast as possible and no later than by the end of the project.

Answer:

Which data usage licenses are you going to provide? Creative Common licenses can be linked to different permission levels (BY, SA, NC, ND). We recommend crediting the creator of the data as a minimum (CC-BY license). Additional permissions may include that derivatives/redistributions must have identical license (CC-BY-SA) and/or that only non-commercial use of the data is allowed (CC-BY-SA-NC). When all copy rights to the data are relinquished, use the CC0 license.

Answer:

Do you intend to add a PID/DOI/accession number to your dataset(s)? If already available, please list them here.

Answer:

What are the expected costs for data sharing? How will these costs be covered?

Answer:

Will there be scientific papers published using the data of the project? If yes, what are the expected costs associated with publication of the papers and how will these costs be covered? Add this information in the "Additional information" box below.

- Yes
- No

Answer: